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Scanning the Issue

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The current issue of The European Journal of Research and Development (Vol 2, Issue 3, October 2022) contains 3 articles.

Bluetooth Low Energy-based Indoor Localization using Artificial Intelligence

Moses Y. Ndebugre, Tülay Yıldırım

1 - 15

Anxiety Levels of General Surgery Patients and Frequency of Visiting the Hospital in Covid-19 Pandemic Period

Hasan Uzer, Şaban Karayağız

16 - 25

Innovation as an accelerating effect on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita

Metin Gürler

26 - 44